

Weed Control with Flaming and Cultivations in Sunflower^A

Ayşe ÖZEN^{1*}, Selçuk ARSLAN², Nihat TURSUN³

Abstract: This study aimed to evaluate the effects of different flame weeding applications on five weed species and on yield in sunflower cultivation. A field experiment was conducted using nine different treatments and a control. Six flame weeding treatments were applied using two LPG doses (60 and 75 kg ha⁻¹) and three application techniques (surface, between-row, and cross-flaming). In addition, to compare flame weeding with mechanical control, three treatments were established: flame applications combined with tillage and hoeing, and hoeing alone. Weeds at three different growth stages were treated, and visual control rates (%) were assessed at 1, 7, and 14 days after treatment (DAT), with four replications. At 14 DAT, dry matter was determined using the oven drying method. The effectiveness of flame treatments was evaluated by comparing dry matter with the control. For sunflowers, head diameter, plant height, and seed weight were measured, and treatment effects on yield were analyzed using multiple comparison tests. The highest yield (2446 kg ha⁻¹) was obtained from the combined treatment of flaming (60 kg ha⁻¹) and hoeing. When weed control efficiency was considered independently, the most effective result was achieved with flame application at 75 kg ha⁻¹.

Keywords: Mechanical weed control, Weed flaming, Sunflower, Yield.

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***Corresponding Author:** ¹ Ayşe ÖZEN, Bursa Uludağ University, Institute of Natural and Applied Sciences, Department of Biosystem Engineering, Bursa, Türkiye, ayseozene@gmail.com, ORCID: 0000-0001-6275-6565

² Selçuk ARSLAN, Bursa Uludağ University, Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Biosystems Engineering, Bursa, Türkiye, sarslan@uludag.edu.tr, ORCID: 0000-0003-4636-1234

³ Nihat TURSUN, Malatya Turgut Özal University, Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Plant Protection, Malatya, Türkiye, nihatt.tursun@ozal.edu.tr, ORCID: 0000-0002-8765-0326

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Introduction

Weeds are defined as plants that grow spontaneously in agricultural fields, other than the cultivated crops, and compete with the crop for essential resources such as light, water, and nutrients, thereby causing more harm than benefit. In addition to their competitive effects, some weed species are toxic to humans and animals, serve as hosts for pests and diseases, and increase production costs by hindering soil tillage and harvesting operations. Particularly in organic agriculture, weeds are considered one of the most significant factors limiting crop yield (Ulloa et al., 2010; Ulloa et al., 2011; Wszelaki, 2007).

Despite the implementation of control measures, yield losses of 30-35% may still occur due to weeds, pests, and diseases. In the absence of effective management, these losses may increase to 70-75% on average and can reach up to 100% in certain crops (Birişik, 2018). Globally, there are approximately 7,000 weed species in agricultural systems, of which 200-300 are considered highly problematic. In Türkiye, around 1,800 weed species have been identified (Arıkan and Elibüyük, 2015). The diversity of agroecological conditions further complicates weed management, as Türkiye alone has 24 million hectares of arable land, 30 agroecological regions, and 165 commercially cultivated plant species. Organic agriculture is practiced in 172 countries worldwide, covering approximately 43.7 million hectares and involving about 2.3 million producers (Yıldız et al., 2018).

Various weed control methods are available, including cultural, physical, mechanical, biological, and chemical approaches, which can be applied individually or in an integrated manner (Arıkan and Elibüyük, 2015; Mainardis et al., 2020). Among these, chemical control through herbicides remains the most widely used method. However, increasing concerns regarding environmental pollution, human health risks, and herbicide resistance have led to restrictions on their use. In addition, the growing interest in organic agriculture and the limited availability of approved inputs highlight the need for alternative, environmentally friendly weed management strategies (Bayat et al., 2017; Martelloni et al., 2019). In this context, flame weeding can be used for weed control in garden plants (leafy greens, asparagus, garlic), fruit trees (grapes, kiwi, hazelnuts) and arable crops (maize, potatoes, clover) (Cedrola, 2024).

Flame weeding is one such alternative method, particularly suitable for organic systems. This technique involves the application of a high-temperature flame to disrupt plant cell structures, leading to desiccation and plant death. Its effectiveness depends on several factors, including application dose, timing, and weed growth stage.

In sunflower production, early-season weed competition is critical. If weed control is not achieved within the first four weeks after crop emergence, significant reductions in plant height and head diameter may occur. The most severe yield losses are typically observed during the first 1-1.5 months after emergence (Uyar, 2019). Therefore, timely and effective weed management is essential, particularly during early growth stages.

In this context, the study aims to investigate the effects of two LPG doses (60 and 75 kg ha⁻¹) with different flame application techniques (between-row, intra-row, and surface), and their combination with hoeing on weed control rates and sunflower yield.

Materials and Methods

This experiment was conducted in a sunflower field affiliated with Bursa Uludağ University, Faculty of Agriculture, during the 2020 growing season. The soil texture of the experimental field was classified as medium-

heavy (clay loam). Two different flaming machines were used in the study (Figure 1). The surface flamer (intra-row) had a working width of 2 m and was equipped with eight torches directed toward the target at a 30° angle. The between-row flamer had a working width of 3 m and was positioned to target the inter-row spaces. Both flammers were mounted on a New Holland TD95D tractor. The necessary procedures and adjustments for calibration of the flammers were determined in previous studies (Asan, 2019; Turaloğlu, 2019). Cross-flaming was performed by combining intra-row (surface) and between-row flaming operations in a single pass. For this purpose, both flammers were operated simultaneously, exposing both the crop rows and the inter-row spaces to the flame.

Figure 1. Two types of flaming machines used on the row: (a) a between row flamer with a working width of 3 m, and (b) an intra row (surface) flamer with a working width of 2 m.

Various materials were used for weed monitoring and experimental measurements, including sticks and string for marking plot boundaries, precision scales, a measuring tape, a calliper, scissors for cutting, paper bags for sample collection, crates for transporting weeds, and an oven for drying.

In the sunflower field, species were identified through visual observation based on their morphological characteristics. In each plot, plant species present at different growth stages were determined and recorded. Five different weed species were identified and included in the experiment: *Convolvulus arvensis L.*, *Cynodon dactylon L.*, *Sinapis arvensis L.*, *Hibiscus trionum L.*, and *Xanthium strumarium L.* The visuals of the weeds used in the study are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Flame-treated weeds in the experiment

The gas pressure, flaming height, and gas doses required for calibration were determined according to Arslan et al. (2016). Accordingly, the gas pressure was set to 0.2 MPa (2 bar), with the flamer positioned 20 cm above the target and operated at a 30° angle from the vertical. Gas doses were adjusted by varying the forward speed of the flamer between 1.8 and 7.2 km h⁻¹, corresponding to application rates of 15-90 kg ha⁻¹.

The tractor was operated over a distance of 40 m with the machine attached, and the appropriate gear range and engine speed were determined to achieve the desired forward speeds. Table 1 shows the treatments used in this study. Table 2 presents the LPG application rates, gear settings, tractor engine speeds, and the required gas pressure for the flamer to accurately apply the desired gas rates (Sefil, 2021).

Table 1. Different treatments tested in the experiment

T1	Between-row flaming at 60 kg ha ⁻¹
T2	Surface flaming at 60 kg ha ⁻¹
T3	Cross-flaming at 60 kg ha ⁻¹
T4	Between-row flaming at 75 kg ha ⁻¹
T5	Surface flaming at 75 kg ha ⁻¹
T6	Cross-flaming at 75 kg ha ⁻¹
T7	Cross-flaming at 60 kg ha ⁻¹ combined with hoeing
T8	Cross-flaming at 75 kg ha ⁻¹ combined with hoeing
T9	Hoeing only
K	Control

Table 2. LPG dose, gear, engine speed, and gas pressure required for flamer

LPG dose (kg/ha)	Gear*	Engine speed (min ⁻¹)	Gas pressure (bar)
60	T2V4	1250	2.25
75	T2V3	1375	2.5

Sunflowers were planted in the first week of May and harvested on September 3. Weed control treatments were initiated on June 7, 2020, four weeks after planting, and the experimental design was established accordingly. Studies were conducted according to the randomized complete block design. In the trial layout, each plot was 70 m long and 3 m wide. In treatments T1-T6, both weed monitoring and sunflower yield and yield components were evaluated, whereas in treatments T7-T9, only sunflower yield and yield components were assessed.

Flame applications were carried out according to three different growth stages of the weeds, i.e., 2-4 leaf stage (V2-V4), 4-6 leaf stage (V6-V8), and 10-12 leaf stage (V10-V12).

The effects of flame treatments on weeds were evaluated visually as weed control rates (%) at 1, 7, and 14 days after treatment (DAT). At DAT 14, weeds were uprooted, fresh weights were recorded, and then oven-dried at 105 °C for 24 h to determine dry weights. Weed response was assessed based on plant height, dry matter content, and fresh-dry weight differences. Each weed species was monitored with four replications, and visual damage assessments were recorded at each observation time.

The 14-day interval for destructive dry matter sampling was selected based on established protocols in thermal weed control research. This timing allows sufficient opportunity for early regrowth to become detectable, particularly in perennial species, while still capturing the immediate effects of the treatment (Ulloa et al., 2010; Ulloa et al., 2011). Earlier assessments (3-7 DAT) might overestimate long-term control because temporary wilting or superficial burning may not result in plant death, whereas later assessments (≥ 28 DAT) prolong the experimental period and introduce confounding factors such as inter-specific competition and changing environmental conditions (Martelloni et al., 2019; Vanhala et al., 2004). Therefore, the 14-day assessment provides a practical and scientifically sound balance for evaluating both the initial damage caused by flaming and the early regrowth response.

Sunflower yield and yield components were determined through manual sampling. Before harvest, field moisture content was estimated by collecting sunflower heads from three locations within the treated area, measuring fresh and dry weights (105 °C, 24 h), and calculating moisture content. Harvesting was conducted when seed moisture decreased below 10 % (Kaya et al., 2020).

Sunflower heads were hand-harvested (September 3, 2020), and head height and diameter were measured. From each plot, 10 heads per row were collected with four replications. Heads were threshed, the seeds were dried under ambient conditions for approximately one week, and seed weights were measured to calculate the yield.

The evaluated parameters included visual weed control (%), weed root and shoot lengths, fresh and dry weights (g), sunflower plant height (cm), head diameter (cm), and grain yield (kg ha⁻¹).

The experiment was arranged in a randomized complete block design with four replications. All statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 25.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied separately for each weed species and growth stage combination, and treatment means were compared using Duncan's multiple range test at a significance level of $P \leq 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

The effect of treatments used on dry weight at different weed growth stages is given in Figure 3. Tables 3-7 presents the results of visual observations on the weed control levels at DAT 1, 7, and 14.

Figure 3. Effect of flame application on dry weight of *Convolvulus arvensis*, *Xanthium strumarium*, *Sinapis arvensis*, *Hibiscus trionum*, and *Cynodon dactylon*

The magnitude of dry weight reduction varied markedly by species and growth stage. For annual weeds (*Sinapis*, *Xanthium*, *Hibiscus*), the most effective treatments reduced dry matter by 70-85 % at V2-V4, but only by 30-50 % at V10-V12. In contrast, for perennial weeds (*Convolvulus*, *Cynodon*), even the highest dose (75 kg ha⁻¹) reduced dry weight by no more than 60 % at 14 DAT, and some *Convolvulus* treatments did not differ significantly from the non-flamed control. Among application techniques, cross-flaming (T3, T6) consistently produced the lowest dry weights, followed by surface flaming (T2, T5), while between-row flaming (T1, T4) was the least effective. These results confirm that early-stage cross-flaming is the most efficient strategy for biomass reduction, but that perennial weeds remain capable of regrowth regardless of the technique used.

Flame application provided high initial weed control across all species; however, control rates consistently declined at 7 and 14 days after treatment (DAT), indicating regrowth, particularly in perennial species.

Table 3. Visually evaluated weed control rates of flaming on *Convolvulus arvensis* on days 1, 7, and 14

%	Day 1			Day 7			Day 14		
	V2-V4	V6-V8	V10-V12	V2-V4	V6-V8	V10-V12	V2-V4	V6-V8	V10-V12
T1	96 aA (1.74)	75 bB (10)	66.67 bB (2.89)	56.67 aB (5.78)	70 aA (26.46)	68.34 aA (2.89)	35 aA (8.67)	56.67 aA (10.41)	58.34 aA (14.44)
T2	95 aA (0)	83.34 bAB (5.78)	66.67 cB (7.64)	70 aAB (8.67)	80 aA (5)	61.67 aA (16.08)	35 aA (0)	43.34 aAB (7.64)	41.67 aAB (2.89)
T3	91.67 aA (2.89)	80 aB (5)	78.34 aAB (16.08)	83.34 aA (11.55)	68.34 aA (7.64)	75 aA (18.03)	50 aA (0)	40 aAB (10)	38.34 aAB (11.55)
T4	94.34 aA (4.05)	85 abAB (5)	80 bAB (10)	80 aA (13.23)	76.67 aA (11.55)	75 aA (5)	35 aA (13.23)	31.67 aB (11.55)	31.67 aB (5.78)
T5	91.67 aA (5.78)	91.67 aA (5.78)	86.67 aA (5.78)	83.34 aA (12.59)	88.34 aA (7.64)	76.67 aA (5)	46.67 aA (5.78)	50 aA (5)	50 aA (0)
T6	91.67 aA (2.89)	85 aAB (5)	86.67 aA (2.89)	85 aA (10)	76.67 aA (5.78)	75 aA (7.64)	40 aA (13.23)	51.67 aA (10.41)	38.34 aAB (2.89)
K	0 aB (0)	0 aC (0)	0 aC (0)	0 aC (0)	0 aB (0)	0 aB (0)	0 aB (0)	0 aC (0)	0 aB (0)

In all tables, upper case means horizontal analysis, lower case means vertical analysis, e means missing data and ns means insignificant. Values in parentheses indicate standard deviation (SD) of the mean (n = 4).

For *Convolvulus arvensis*, control rates reached 91-96 % at 1 DAT (V2-V4 stage) but decreased to 35-50 % at 14 DAT (Table 3). This decline is attributed to its perennial nature and capacity for regrowth. Similar trends were observed at later growth stages, with reduced effectiveness as leaf number increased. Dry weight analysis (Figure 3) confirmed that flame treatments significantly reduced biomass compared to the control, although dry matter increased with plant maturity, highlighting the importance of early-stage control (preferably V2-V4). The regrowth capacity of *Convolvulus arvensis* was quantified by the decline in control rates. Most of this decline occurred within the first 7 days, where control had already fallen to 76 %. This rapid loss of efficacy indicates that a single flaming application provides effective suppression for only 7-10 days in this perennial species. Without repeated treatment, the weed population is likely to recover to pre-treatment levels.

Table 4. Visually evaluated weed control rates of flaming on *Xanthium strumarium* on days 1, 7, and 14

%	Day 1			Day 7			Day 14		
	V2-V4	V6-V8	V10-V12	V2-V4	V6-V8	V10-V12	V2-V4	V6-V8	V10-V12
T1	90 aA (5)	83.34 aA (2.89)	70 bB (5)	75 aAB (5)	68.34 aAB (7.64)	66.67 aAB (5.78)	68.34 aB (7.64)	43.34 aBB (10.41)	33.34 bA (18.93)
T2	91.67 aA (2.89)	83.34 aA (2.89)	83.34 aA (5.78)	90 aA (5)	60 cB (8.67)	73.34 bA (2.89)	88.34 aA (2.89)	51.67 bB (10.41)	50 bA (22.92)
T3	91.67 aA (2.89)	83.34 aA (2.89)	81.67 aA (2.89)	83.34 aA (2.89)	75 aA (10)	70 aA (10)	78.34 aAB (7.64)	61.67 aAB (12.59)	35 bA (10)
T4	88.34 aA (2.89)	83.34 aA (2.89)	65 bB (10)	71.67 aB (7.64)	71.67 aAB (2.89)	58.34 aB (7.64)	66.67 aB (2.89)	43.34 bB (7.64)	33.34 bA (10.41)
T5	e	90 A (5)	83.34 A (2.89)	E	83.34 A (2.89)	75 A (0)	e	46.67 B (15.28)	55A (0)
T6	93.34 aA (7.64)	85 aA (10)	80 aA (5)	90 aA (8.67)	80 aA (8.67)	76.67 Aa (5.78)	85 aA (13.23)	75 aA (8.67)	48.34 bA (7.64)
K	0 B (0)	0 C (0)	0 C (0)	0 C (0)	0 B (0)				

In all tables, upper case means horizontal analysis, lower case means vertical analysis, e means missing data and ns means insignificant. Values in parentheses indicate standard deviation (SD) of the mean (n = 4).

For *Xanthium strumarium*, control rates ranged between 88–94% (1 DAT) and 65–89% (14 DAT) at early growth stages (Table 4). The highest effectiveness at 14 DAT was observed in T2 and T6 treatments. As in *Convolvulus arvensis*, control efficiency declined with increasing plant size due to enhanced structural resistance and regrowth potential.

Table 5. Visually evaluated weed control rates of flaming on *Sinapis arvensis* on days 1, 7, and 14

%	Day 1			Day 7			Day 14		
	V2-V4	V6-V8	V10-V12	V2-V4	V6-V8	V10-V12	V2-V4	V6-V8	V10-V12
T1	93.34 ab (2.89)	86.67 bA (2.89)	95 aA (5)	81.67 a (2.89)	70 aAB (10)	85 aA (13.23)	76.67 a (2.89)	56.67 aAB (15.28)	76.67 aA (20.21)
T2	e	86.67 A (5.78)	83.34 B (2.89)	E	75.34 A (10.41)	70 AB (5)	e	70 A (5)	53.34 B (5.78)
T3	e	85 A (10)	86.67 AB (2.89)	E	60 B (8.67)	73.34 AB (15.28)	e	36.67 B (16.08)	60 AB (10)
T4	e	85 A (5)	83.34 B (2.89)	E	76.67 A (2.89)	63.34 B (5.78)	e	53.34 AB (12.59)	45 B (5)
T5	e	90 A (0)	91.67 A (5.78)	E	83.34 A (2.89)	90 A (8.67)	e	50 AB (8.67)	53.34 B (5.78)
T6	e	95 A (5)	93.34 A (2.89)	E	86.67 A (11.55)	78.34 AB (15.28)	e	68.34 A (30.14)	50 B (10)
K	0 (0)	0 b (0)	0 b (0)	0 (0)	0 b (0)	0 c (0)	0 (0)	0 c (0)	0 c (0)

In all tables, upper case means horizontal analysis, lower case means vertical analysis, e means missing data and ns means insignificant. Values in parentheses indicate standard deviation (SD) of the mean (n = 4).

In *Sinapis arvensis*, flame treatments were generally effective during early growth stages, with control rates of 85-95 % at 1 DAT and 36-70 % at 14 DAT (Table 5). Due to the non-homogeneous distribution of weed populations within the field and the asynchronous germination observed in *Sinapis arvensis*, it was observed that some plots did not contain individuals at the V2-V4 stage at the time of treatment, whereas plants at later growth stages (V6-V8, V10-V12) could be found in the same plots. The most effective treatments were T2 and T6. However, in later growth stages (V10-V12), variability increased, and in some cases, dry matter exceeded control levels, indicating reduced treatment efficiency beyond the V6-V8 stage.

For *Hibiscus trionum*, high initial control (83-92 %) declined substantially by 14 DAT (10-60 %). Although some inconsistencies were observed (possibly due to measurement variability or plant morphology), flame treatments generally reduced dry matter compared with the control, particularly in V6-V8 stages (Figure 3). Smaller plant size and possible shielding effects may explain deviations observed at early stages.

Table 6. Visually evaluated weed control rates of flaming on *Hibiscus trionum* on days 1, 7, and 14

%	Day 1			Day 7			Day 14		
	V2-V4	V6-V8	V10-V12	V2-V4	V6-V8	V10-V12	V2-V4	V6-V8	V10-V12
T1	90 aA (5)	85 aA (5)	85 aA (0)	80 aA (10)	56.67 bB (11.5)	53.34 bB (2.89)	60 aA (13.23)	41.67 aA (20.21)	10 bB (0)
T2	85 aA (5)	85 aA (0)	78.34 aAB (2.89)	73.34 aA (11.55)	73.34 aA (2.89)	61.67 aAB (10.41)	38.34 aB (14.44)	36.67 aA (7.64)	35 aA (5)
T3	91.67 aA (2.89)	83.34 bAB (2.89)	85 bA (0)	81.67 aA (11.55)	76.67 aA (16.08)	76.67 aA (2.89)	53.34 aAB (2.89)	40 aA (13.23)	51.67 aA (2.89)
T4	88.34 aA (2.89)	76.67 bB (2.89)	73.34 bB (2.89)	81.67 aA (2.89)	63.34 bAB (2.89)	56.67 cAB (2.89)	50 aAB (8.67)	41.67 aA (2.89)	13.34 bB (2.89)
T5	86.67 A (5.78)	88.34 aA (7.64)	83.34 aA (2.89)	78.34 aA (5.78)	85 aA (8.67)	58.34b AB (2.89)	55 aAB (10)	41.67 aA (22.55)	40 aA (5)
T6	83.34 aA (12.59)	83.34 aAB (2.89)	78.34 aAb (7.64)	75 aA (18.03)	71.67 aAB (7.64)	66.67 aA (12.59)	58.34 aAB (14.44)	48.34 abA (2.89)	36.67 bA (5.78)
K	0 b (0)	0 c (0)	0 b (0)	0 b (0)	0 b (0)	0 b (0)	0 c (0)	0 b (0)	0 b (0)

In all tables, upper case means horizontal analysis, lower case means vertical analysis, e means missing data and ns means insignificant. Values in parentheses indicate standard deviation (SD) of the mean (n = 4).

In *Cynodon dactylon*, control rates were initially high (83-99%) but decreased to 33-92 % at 14 DAT depending on growth stage and treatment (Table 7). The most effective treatments were T2 and T5. As a perennial species, its resistance increased with plant maturity, and dry weight reductions were less consistent compared to annual species.

The marked decline in control rates observed in *Convolvulus arvensis* and *Cynodon dactylon* between 1 DAT (91-99 %) and 14 DAT (33-50 %) can be attributed primarily to the morphological and physiological characteristics of these perennial species. Both species possess extensive below ground storage organs deep seated rhizomes in *Cynodon dactylon* and a well-developed taproot system with lateral roots in *Convolvulus arvensis* which are largely unaffected by surface flame exposure. Thermal damage is restricted to above ground tissues, whereas meristematic tissues located at or below the soil surface retain sufficient carbohydrate reserves to initiate rapid shoot regeneration within days of treatment (Ascard, 1995; Vanhala et al., 2004). Furthermore, the waxy and

pubescent leaf surfaces of *Convolvulus arvensis* may confer additional resistance to heat transfer, reducing the lethal thermal dose required to cause irreversible cell damage. These findings are consistent with the broader literature indicating that a single flaming application is insufficient for long term suppression of perennial weeds, and that repeated treatments at 7-10 day intervals are necessary to deplete root reserves and prevent regrowth.

Table 7. Visually evaluated weed control rates of flaming on *Cynodon dactylon* on days 1, 7, and 14.

%	Day 1			Day 7			Day 14		
	V2-V4	V6-V8	V10-V12	V2-V4	V6-V8	V10-V12	V2-V4	V6-V8	V10-V12
T1	95 aA (0)	88.34 aA (2.89)	85 aA (10)	70 aB (5)	78.34 aA (12.59)	68.34 aA (7.64)	35 aB (8.67)	45 aB (8.67)	35 aB (10)
T2	98.34 aA (2.89)	90 bA (5)	76.67 cAB (2.89)	98.34 aA (2.89)	66.67 bAB (11.55)	60 bAB (8.67)	91.67 aA (14.44)	56.67 bA (10.41)	41.67 bB (2.89)
T3	83.34 aB (5.78)	75 aB (5)	66.67 aB (14.44)	75 aB (13.23)	60 abB (5)	55 bB (8.67)	56.67 aA (7.64)	41.67 bB (2.89)	38.34 bB (7.64)
T4	83.34 aB (10.41)	90 aA (5)	83.34 aA (2.89)	76.67 aB (2.89)	71.67 aAB (11.55)	46.67 bB (2.89)	50 abAB (15)	61.67 aA (2.89)	41.67 bB (5.78)
T5	96.67 aA (2.89)	93.34 aA (2.89)	83.34 bA (2.89)	96.67 aA (2.89)	78.34 bA (2.89)	70 cA (5)	91.67 aA (7.64)	65 bA (10)	55 bA (5)
T6	85 aB (0)	80 aB (5)	81.67 aA (2.89)	78.34 aB (2.89)	76.67 aA (7.64)	78.34 aA (2.89)	56.67 aA (7.64)	43.34 bB (2.89)	33.34 cB (2.89)
K	0 c (0)	0 c (0)	0 c (0)	0 c (0)	0 c (0)	0 c (0)	0 b (0)	0 c (0)	0 c (0)

In all tables, upper case means horizontal analysis, lower case means vertical analysis, e means missing data and ns means insignificant. Values in parentheses indicate standard deviation (SD) of the mean (n = 4).

Overall, flame treatments were effective in reducing weed biomass and achieving high initial control; however, their long-term effectiveness decreased due to regrowth, especially in perennial weeds. Across all species, earlier growth stages (V2-V4) were the most suitable for effective control, while treatments applied beyond the V6-V8 stage showed reduced efficacy. Below-ground organs of perennial species (rhizomes, tubers, and thickened roots) may not be damaged by flaming treatment. Even if the above-ground parts are burned, the plant retains the capacity to regenerate new shoots. Therefore, a single flaming application may prove insufficient; repeated applications are more effective. These findings highlight the importance of timing in flame weeding applications to maximize control efficiency and minimize weed recovery.

The effect of treatments on sunflower traits is summarized in Table 8. Flame application had limited effects on sunflower morphological traits, as head diameter and plant height did not differ significantly among treatments. However, grain yield was notably influenced by treatment type. The highest yield (2446 kg ha⁻¹) was obtained from T7 (60 kg ha⁻¹ cross-flaming combined with hoeing), followed by T3 (60 kg ha⁻¹ cross application, 2371 kg ha⁻¹). In contrast, the lowest yield was recorded in the untreated control (1869 kg ha⁻¹), while T6 also resulted in a relatively low yield (1959 kg ha⁻¹). Compared to the control, yield increases ranged from 4.8 % to 30.9 %, indicating that integrating flame application with mechanical control can significantly enhance productivity.

Table 8. The effect of treatments on sunflower head diameter, stem height, and yield

Treatment	Head diameter (cm)	Stem height (cm)	Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Increase (%)
T1	13.57 b (2.67)	132.22 a (9.18)	2078 abc (4.72)	11.2
T2	14 b (2.5)	133.1 a (13.07)	2255 abc (11.06)	20.7
T3	15.51 a (2.51)	131.73 a (8.5)	2370 ab (9.25)	26.8
T4	13.35 b (1.56)	132.12 a (9.94)	2114 abc (8.41)	13.1
T5	13.63 b (1.64)	138.79 a (14.59)	2056.3 abc (20.65)	10.0
T6	13.76 b (2.85)	138.03 a (5.78)	1959 bc (27.32)	4.8
T7	14.31 ab (2.01)	137.85 a (10.3)	2446 ab (35.29)	30.9
T8	13.83 b (1.91)	138.25 a (13.87)	2323 a (23.85)	24.3
T9	13.36 b (2.22)	140.6 a (13.63)	2089 abc (26.45)	11.8
K	13.47 b (3.17)	133.95 a (11.99)	1869 c (29.73)	0
F	2.250*	0.860ns	21.31*	

Values followed by the same letter are not significantly different ($p>0.05$). One-way ANOVA was performed separately for each parameter (head diameter, stem height, and yield); values in parentheses indicate standard deviation (SD) of the mean ($n = 4$).

A comparison of the three flaming techniques reveals clear differences in efficacy. At the same LPG dose (60 kg ha⁻¹), cross-flaming (T3) consistently achieved higher weed control rates than surface (T2) or between-row (T1) flaming across all species and growth stages. For instance, in *Xanthium strumarium* at V6-V8, control at 14 DAT was 61.7 % for T3 versus 51.7 % for T2 and 43.3 % for T1. However, cross-flaming at the higher dose (T6, 75 kg) caused visible crop damage, resulting in the lowest sunflower yield among flame-only treatments (1959 kg ha⁻¹). Surface flaming provided intermediate control, while between-row flaming was the least effective but also the safest for the crop. Therefore, for organic sunflower production, cross-flaming at 60 kg ha⁻¹ combined with hoeing (T7) offers the best balance of weed control and crop safety.

Increasing the LPG dose from 60 to 75 kg ha⁻¹ did not proportionally improve weed control, particularly at early growth stages. For example, in *Sinapis arvensis* at V2-V4, control rates at 1 DAT were 93.3 % for T1 (60 kg) versus 95 % for T4 (75 kg) – a negligible difference. At later stages (V10-V12), the higher dose provided a modest improvement (e.g., 83.3 % vs. 91.7 % for the same species), but this came at the cost of crop safety. Notably, T6 (75 kg cross-flaming) resulted in the lowest sunflower yield (1959 kg ha⁻¹) among flame-only treatments, likely due to phytotoxic damage. Thus, dose elevation offers only marginal benefits when applications are delayed beyond V6-V8, while increasing the risk of crop injury.

The variability in treatment effectiveness can be attributed to weed density, species composition, and plant morphology. Dense weed populations and overlapping canopies reduced flame penetration, thereby limiting treatment efficiency. Moreover, weed biological traits, such as root and stem development, played a critical role in resistance to thermal stress. Other studies have shown that, when applied at the appropriate time, the burning technique effectively reduces weed density and, under certain conditions, provides a level of control comparable to that achieved through chemical applications; this makes the technique a viable method for sustainable weed management (Borowy and Dzida, 2022; Chehade et al., 2018).

Consistent with previous studies (Asav and Serim, 2019; Uyar, 2019), flame treatments were most effective at early growth stages. Literature indicates that achieving approximately 90 % weed control requires significantly higher LPG doses as weed development progresses (Asan, 2019), whereas lower doses (30-40 kg ha⁻¹) are sufficient at early stages (Sefil, 2021). Similarly, Ascard (1994) reported that 40-70 kg ha⁻¹ LPG is required depending on the leaf stage for effective control.

In the present study, treatment effectiveness varied across species and growth stages. For example, *Cynodon dactylon* showed high control rates under T2 and T5 treatments, while *Xanthium strumarium* responded best to T2 and T6. *Sinapis arvensis* and *Hibiscus trionum* were more effectively controlled at earlier stages, whereas *Convolvulus arvensis*, as a perennial species, showed reduced long-term control due to regrowth capacity. Across all species, treatment efficiency declined with increasing leaf number, reflecting enhanced structural resistance and regrowth potential.

Comparisons with previous studies highlight that maximum yields are typically achieved under weed-free or integrated control conditions (Başaran et al., 2017; Tursun et al., 2017; Yücel, 2011). Similarly, Uyar (2019) demonstrated that combining flaming with hoeing improves yield performance. The present findings support this, as the highest yield was obtained from combined flame and hoeing treatment (T7), whereas sole flame applications showed variable performance.

A two-way interaction between treatment type and weed growth stage was evident across all five species. For annual weeds (*Sinapis arvensis*, *Hibiscus trionum*, *Xanthium strumarium*), advancing from V2-V4 to V10-V12 reduced mean control rates by 40-50 % at 14 DAT, regardless of LPG dose. In contrast, for perennial species (*Convolvulus arvensis*, *Cynodon dactylon*), the decline in control from 1 DAT to 14 DAT was independent of growth stage, indicating that below-ground regenerative capacity is the dominant factor limiting long-term efficacy. This differential response suggests that timing is more critical for annuals, whereas perennial weeds require repeated interventions irrespective of application timing. Overall, flame weeding is an effective alternative, particularly in early growth stages (V2-V4), and can contribute to yield improvement when integrated with mechanical control methods. However, its effectiveness declines at later growth stages (beyond V6-V8), especially for perennial weeds. The reduction in control rates over time further suggests that repeated applications (e.g., 7-10 days after initial treatment) may be necessary to suppress regrowth. While flame treatments can negatively affect crop yield under certain conditions, optimized timing and integration with other control methods can enhance both weed management and sunflower productivity.

Conclusion

This study evaluated the effects of flame weeding using two LPG doses (60 and 75 kg ha⁻¹) and three application techniques (between-row, surface, and cross-flaming) on sunflower yield and weed control. A total of nine treatments were tested, including flaming alone, flaming combined with hoeing, and hoeing alone.

The highest sunflower yield was obtained from the combined application of 60 kg ha⁻¹ flaming and hoeing (T7), followed by 60 kg ha⁻¹ cross flaming (T3), with comparable yield levels. Although most treatments showed similar weed control performance, the T6 treatment (75 kg ha⁻¹ cross) provided the highest weed suppression. However, this higher dose also caused crop damage, resulting in reduced yield.

The results indicate that moderate flame doses (e.g., 60 kg ha⁻¹) applied at appropriate growth stages can achieve a balance between effective weed control and crop safety. Nevertheless, due to weed regrowth, particularly

in perennial species, flame weeding should be integrated with additional practices such as hoeing or repeated applications to improve long-term effectiveness.

In general, flame weeding offers a promising alternative to chemical herbicides, particularly in organic farming systems. However, the success of this method depends on optimally adjusting the application rate, timing, and technique to ensure adequate weed control whilst minimising crop damage. To enhance the method's practical applicability and support its commercialisation, further research into integrated and repeated applications is recommended.

Conflict of Interest

The author(s) declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this manuscript.

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